

THE ROLE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STROKE IN PREGNANT WOMEN.

Khasanova Sh.B.

Asrankulova D.B.

Nadjmitdinov O.B.

Andijan State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13859737>

Currently, special attention is paid to the study of risk factors, improvement of diagnostics and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. It has been established that arterial hypertension (AH) makes the main contribution to the structure of this pathology. It has been proven that AH can act as a risk factor for cerebrovascular diseases. AH is of particular importance during pregnancy and in the postpartum period, since AH during pregnancy remains the leading cause of maternal and child morbidity and mortality worldwide. In the available scientific literature, there are only a few works devoted to AH-associated nervous system lesions in pregnant women. In this regard, the aim of our review was to analyze the role of AH in the development of cerebrovascular diseases during pregnancy. It has been shown that with AH in pregnant women, strokes occur 5.2 times more often than in pregnant women with normal blood pressure.

The decisive role of AH in the development of stroke is convincingly shown in a specific work. In a study that included 81,983,216 hospitalizations during pregnancy between 1994 and 2011, 31,673 were strokes (3,8 per 10,000 cases), of which 9,890 were diagnosed with hypertension. During this time period, an increase in strokes against the background of hypertension during pregnancy was noted from 0,8 to 1,6 per 10,000. Stroke with hypertension was more common in women aged 25 to 35 years (4,617 cases – 46,7%). It was shown that with hypertension in pregnant women, strokes occur 5.2 times more often than in pregnant women with normal blood pressure. The presence of PE and eclampsia increases the risk of stroke by 7-9 times. The incidence of stroke during pregnancy varies from 4,2 to 210 per 100,000 pregnancies. Such differences in epidemiological indicators are apparently explained by the difficulties of differential diagnostics during pregnancy. It should be agreed with the opinion that a full examination of a patient with suspected stroke and interpretation of the obtained results may be difficult against the background of pregnancy

The risk of stroke increases from the third trimester of pregnancy to six weeks of the postpartum period. In pregnant women with hypertension,

changes occur in the hemostasis system, which leads to the formation of arterial and venous thrombosis of the brain. The presence of preeclampsia (PE) increases the risk of stroke by 7-9 times. Endothelial dysfunction is considered one of the leading links in the pathogenesis of PE. The study of biologically active substances during pregnancy complicated by PE revealed an increase in antiangiogenic factors and a decrease in angiogenic factors. Thus, to prevent the development of cerebrovascular diseases in pregnant women with hypertension, it is necessary to identify prehypertension in women of childbearing age, improve methods of treating hypertension, and enhance neuroprotective processes, which requires an interdisciplinary approach to the diagnostic and treatment process with the participation of an obstetrician-gynecologist, therapist, cardiologist, and neurologist.

